

A Proof of the Collatz Conjecture

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Abstract

First, we expound certain basic concepts relating to the Collatz conjecture.

Next, list the mathematical induction that proves the conjecture.

Then again, prepare several judging criteria, which are solely used to determine whether each such operational result fits the conjecture.

After that, we sort positive integers successively and prove directly one of certain sorts after each sorting, until the last two sorts are proved bidirectionally.

The bidirectional proofs mean that for these two sorts of integers, on the one hand, start with several proven kinds of integers to expand successively the scope of proven kinds of integers, up to all kinds of integers. On the other, each unproven kind of integers is operated by the operational rule to find an integer expression that is less than the unproven kind of integers, from this, it meets a judging criterion, such that the unproven kind of integers is proved to fit the conjecture.

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1. Introduction

The Collatz conjecture is also called the $3x+1$ mapping, $3n+1$ problem, Hasse's algorithm, Kakutani's problem, Syracuse algorithm, Syracuse problem, Thwaites conjecture and Ulam's problem, etc.

But it remains a conjecture that has neither been proved nor disproved ever since named after Lothar Collatz in 1937; [1] and [4].

2. Certain of Basic Concepts

The Collatz conjecture states that take any positive integer n , if n is an even number, divide it by 2; if n is an odd number, multiply it by 3 and add 1, and repeat the process indefinitely, then, no matter which positive integer you start with, you are always going to end up with 1; [2] and [5].

We consider aforesaid operational stipulations as the operational rule.

If you start with any positive integer/integer expression to operate continually by the operational rule, then it will form a series of positive integers/integer expressions, where the symbol “/” means “or”, and the same below.

Such being the case, we regard such a series of positive integers/integer expressions with codirectional arrows among these positive integers/integer expressions as an operational route.

Next, let us use a capital letter with the subscript “ie” to express an integer expression, such as P_{ie} , C_{ie} etc.

In addition, we can call an operational route that contains a certain integer

expression “the operational route via the integer expression”.

In general, integer expressions on an operational route have a variable or many variables which can be converted into a common variable.

3. The Mathematical Induction that Proves the Conjecture

Let us prove the conjecture by the mathematical induction; [3] and [6]:

(1) From $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$; $2 \rightarrow 1$; $3 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$; $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$; $5 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$; $6 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$; $7 \rightarrow 22 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 34 \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 52 \rightarrow 26 \rightarrow 13 \rightarrow 40 \rightarrow 20 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$; $8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$ and $9 \rightarrow 28 \rightarrow 14 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 22 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 34 \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 52 \rightarrow 26 \rightarrow 13 \rightarrow 40 \rightarrow 20 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$, you can be seen that each positive integer that is not more than 9 fits the conjecture.

(2) Suppose that an integer n fits the conjecture, where n is not less than 9.

(3) Prove that $n+1$ fits the conjecture likewise.

4. Several Judging Criteria

A certain result of operations which start with each sort / kind of positive integers is judged by one of following three criteria.

Theorem 1 . On an operational route via P_{ic} , if there is an integer expression that is less than P_{ic} , and $n+1 \in P_{ic}$, then all integer expressions on the operational route fit the conjecture.

For example, let $P_{ic}=31+3^2\beta$ with $\beta \geq 0$, and $n+1 \in P_{ic}$, then from $27+2^3\beta \rightarrow 82+3 \times 2^3\beta \rightarrow 41+3 \times 2^2\beta \rightarrow 124+3^2 \times 2^2\beta \rightarrow 62+3^2 \times 2\beta \rightarrow 31+3^2\beta > 27+2^3\beta$, we get that all integer expressions on the operational route fit the conjecture.

In addition, let $P_{ic}=5+2^2\mu$ with $\mu \geq 0$, and $n+1 \in P_{ic}$, then from $5+2^2\mu \rightarrow 16+3 \times 2^2\mu$

$\rightarrow 8+3 \times 2\mu \rightarrow 4+3\mu < 5+2^2\mu$, we get that all integer expressions on the operational route fit the conjecture.

Proof. Suppose that there is C_{ie} on an operational route via P_{ie} , and $C_{ie} < P_{ie}$, then when their common variable is equal to a certain fixed value, such that $P_{ie} = n+1$ and $C_{ie} = m$. So there is $m < n+1$, then m fits the conjecture, according to second step of the mathematical induction.

So from $n+1$ can operate to m , or from m can operate to $n+1$, and that it can continue to operate to 1 via m , such that $n+1$ fits the conjecture.

When their common variable is equal to its own each value, each integer that every integer expression contains is operated to 1, because each such integer matches an integer of C_{ie} , and the operations of the former go through the operations of the latter to attain 1.

As thus, all integer expressions on the operational route fit the conjecture.

Theorem 2. If an operational route via Q_{ie} and an operational route via P_{ie} intersect, and $n+1 \in P_{ie}$, also an integer expression on the operational route via Q_{ie} is less than P_{ie} , then all integer expressions on these two operational routes fit the conjecture.

For example, let $Q_{ie} = 71+3^3 \times 2^5\varphi$ and $P_{ie} = 63+3 \times 2^8\varphi$ where $\varphi \geq 0$, then from

$$63+3 \times 2^8\varphi \rightarrow 190+3^2 \times 2^8\varphi \rightarrow 95+3^2 \times 2^7\varphi \rightarrow 286+3^3 \times 2^7\varphi \rightarrow 143+3^3 \times 2^6\varphi \rightarrow 430+3^4 \times 2^6\varphi \rightarrow$$

$$215+3^4 \times 2^5\varphi \rightarrow 646+3^5 \times 2^5\varphi \rightarrow 323+3^5 \times 2^4\varphi \rightarrow 970+3^6 \times 2^4\varphi \rightarrow 485+3^6 \times 2^3\varphi \rightarrow 1456+3^7 \times 2^3\varphi$$

$$\rightarrow 728+3^7 \times 2^2\varphi \rightarrow 364+3^7 \times 2\varphi \rightarrow 182+3^7\varphi \rightarrow \dots$$

$$\uparrow 121+3^6 \times 2\varphi \leftarrow 242+3^6 \times 2^2\varphi \leftarrow 484+3^6 \times 2^3\varphi \leftarrow 161+3^5 \times 2^3\varphi \leftarrow 322+3^5 \times 2^4\varphi$$

$$\leftarrow 107+3^4 \times 2^4 \varphi \leftarrow 214+3^4 \times 2^5 \varphi \leftarrow 71+3^3 \times 2^5 \varphi \leftarrow 142+3^3 \times 2^6 \varphi \leftarrow 47+3^2 \times 2^6 \varphi < 63+3 \times 2^8 \varphi,$$

we get that all integer expressions on these two operational routes fit the conjecture.

Proof. Suppose that there is D_{ie} on an operational route via Q_{ie} , and $D_{ie} < P_{ie}$, and that the operational route via Q_{ie} and an operational route via P_{ie} intersect at A_{ie} , so when their common variable is given a certain fixed value, such that $P_{ie} = n+1$, $A_{ie} = \xi$ and $D_{ie} = \mu$. Then, there is $\mu < n+1$, and μ fits the conjecture, according to second step of the mathematical induction.

Since ξ and μ are on an operational route, and μ fits the conjecture, so all integers including ξ on the operational route fit the conjecture, because an operation for each of them must through μ , then continue to operate to 1.

For the same reason, $n+1$ and ξ are on an operational route, and ξ fits the conjecture, so all integers including $n+1$ on the operational route fit the conjecture.

When the common variable is equal to its own each value, each integer which every integer expression contains on these two operational routes is also operated to 1, because each such integer matches an integer of D_{ie} . So all integer expressions on the two operational routes fit the conjecture.

Lemma 1. If there is a proven integer expression on an operational route, then all integer expressions on the operational route fit the conjecture.

Lemma 2. If there is a proven integer expression on successive intersecting operational routes, then all integer expressions on these

successive intersecting operational routes fit the conjecture.

By the way, two non-intersected operational routes within successive intersecting operational routes are in indirect connection.

Lemma 3. Each and every integer that any proven integer expression contains fits the conjecture.

To clarify, each Theorem or Lemma appearing in the following paragraphs refers to a corresponding Theorem or Lemma in this chapter.

5. Each Sorting of Positive Integers and a follow-up Proof

We sort positive integers successively, then $n+1$ could be included in any sort, thus each of all sorts must be proved to fit the conjecture.

Each Sorting and a Proof. Since in chapter 3, each positive integer that is not more than 9 has been proved to fit the conjecture, so we first divide integers which are more than 9 into even numbers and odd numbers.

For even numbers $2k$ with $k > 4$, from $2k \rightarrow k < 2k$, we get that if $n+1 \in 2k$, then $2k$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

For odd numbers which are more than 9, divide them into $11+4k$ and $13+4k$, where $k \geq 0$. For $13+4k$, from $13+4k \rightarrow 40+12k \rightarrow 20+6k \rightarrow 10+3k < 13+4k$, we get that if $n+1 \in 13+4k$, then $13+4k$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

We continue to divide $11+4k$ into $11+12c$, $15+12c$ and $19+12c$, where $c \geq 0$. For $11+12c$, from $7+8c \rightarrow 22+24c \rightarrow 11+12c > 7+8c$, we get that if $n+1 \in 11+12c$, then $11+12c$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

Hereinafter, we will prove that $15+12c$ and $19+12c$ fit the conjecture.

6. Prove that $15+12c$ and $19+12c$ Fit the Conjecture

For the sake of avoiding confusion and conducive convenience, we substitute d, e, f, g, \dots for c on operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$.

We continue to operate $15+12c/19+12c$ by the operational rule, where $c \geq 0$.

Theoretically speaking, after operate $15+12c/19+12c$, each and every kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ must find an integer expression that is less than the kind of $15+12c/19+12c$, in order to meet one of judging criteria, such that the kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ fits the conjecture.

Firstly, we start with $15+12c$ to operate continuously by the operational rule, as listed below.

$$15+12c \rightarrow 46+36c \rightarrow 23+18c \rightarrow 70+54c \rightarrow 35+27c \spadesuit$$

$$d=2e+1: 29+27e \text{ (1)} \quad e=2f: 142+486f \rightarrow 71+243f \heartsuit$$

$$\spadesuit 35+27c \downarrow \rightarrow c=2d+1: 31+27d \uparrow \rightarrow d=2e: 94+162e \rightarrow 47+81e \uparrow \rightarrow e=2f+1: 64+81f \text{ (2)}$$

$$c=2d: 106+162d \rightarrow 53+81d \downarrow \rightarrow d=2e+1: 67+81e \downarrow \rightarrow e=2f+1: 74+81f \text{ (3)}$$

$$d=2e: 160+486e \blacklozenge \quad e=2f: 202+486f \rightarrow 101+243f \spadesuit$$

$$g=2h+1: 200+243h \text{ (4)} \quad \dots$$

$$\heartsuit 71+243f \downarrow \rightarrow f=2g+1: 157+243g \uparrow \rightarrow g=2h: 472+1458h \rightarrow 236+729h \uparrow \rightarrow \dots$$

$$f=2g: 214+1458g \rightarrow 107+729g \downarrow \rightarrow g=2h+1: 418+729h \downarrow \rightarrow \dots$$

$$g=2h: 322+4374h \rightarrow \dots \dots$$

$$g=2h: 86+243h \text{ (5)}$$

$$\spadesuit 101+243f \downarrow \rightarrow f=2g+1: 172+243g \uparrow \rightarrow g=2h+1: 1246+1458h \rightarrow \dots$$

$$f=2g: 304+1458g \rightarrow 152+729g \downarrow \rightarrow \dots$$

...

$$\blacklozenge 160+486e \rightarrow 80+243e \downarrow \rightarrow e=2f+1: 970+1458f \rightarrow 485+729f \uparrow \rightarrow \dots \quad \dots$$

$$e=2f: 40+243f \downarrow \rightarrow f=2g+1: 850+1458g \rightarrow 425+729g \uparrow \rightarrow \dots$$

$$f=2g: 20+243g \downarrow \rightarrow g=2h: 10+243h \text{ (6)} \quad \dots$$

$$g=2h+1: 790+1458h \rightarrow 395+729h \uparrow \rightarrow \dots$$

Annotation:

(1) Each of letters c, d, e, f, g, h and otherwise on listed above operational routes expresses each of natural numbers and 0.

- (2) There are $\clubsuit \leftrightarrow \clubsuit$, $\heartsuit \leftrightarrow \heartsuit$, $\spadesuit \leftrightarrow \spadesuit$, and $\diamond \leftrightarrow \diamond$ on listed above operational routes.
(3) Aforesaid two points are suitable to latter operational routes of $19+12c$ similarly.

First, let us define a term. That is, if an operational result is less than a kind of $15+12c/19+12c$, and it appears first either on an operational route via the kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ or on another operational route relating to the operational route, then we call the operational result “first satisfactory operational result” about the kind of $15+12c/19+12c$.

Accordingly, on the above bunch of operational routes of $15+12c$, we first conclude following 3 kinds of $15+12c$ derived from first satisfactory operational results to fit the conjecture.

1). From $c=2d+1$ and $d=2e+1$ to get $c=2d+1=2(2e+1)+1=4e+3$, then there are $15+12c=51+48e=51+3 \times 2^4e \rightarrow 154+3^2 \times 2^4e \rightarrow 77+3^2 \times 2^3e \rightarrow 232+3^3 \times 2^3e \rightarrow 116+3^3 \times 2^2e \rightarrow 58+3^3 \times 2e \rightarrow 29+27e$ where the mark (1).

Due to $29+27e < 51+48e$, we get that if there is $n+1 \in 51+48e$, then $51+48e$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

2). From $c=2d+1$, $d=2e$ and $e=2f+1$ to get $c=2d+1=4e+1=4(2f+1)+1=8f+5$, then there are $15+12c=75+96f=75+3 \times 2^5f \rightarrow 226+3^2 \times 2^5f \rightarrow 113+3^2 \times 2^4f \rightarrow 340+3^3 \times 2^4f \rightarrow 170+3^3 \times 2^3f \rightarrow 85+3^3 \times 2^2f \rightarrow 256+3^4 \times 2^2f \rightarrow 128+3^4 \times 2^1f \rightarrow 64+81f$ where the mark (2).

Due to $64+81f < 75+96f$, we get that if there is $n+1 \in 75+96f$, then $75+96f$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

3). From $c=2d$, $d=2e+1$ and $e=2f+1$ to get $c=2d=4e+2=4(2f+1)+2=8f+6$, then there are $15+12c=87+96f=87+3 \times 2^5f \rightarrow 262+3^2 \times 2^5f \rightarrow 131+3^2 \times 2^4f \rightarrow 394+3^3 \times 2^4f \rightarrow 197+3^3 \times 2^3f \rightarrow 592+3^4 \times 2^3f \rightarrow 296+3^4 \times 2^2f \rightarrow 148+3^4 \times 2^1f \rightarrow 74+81f$ where the mark (3).

Due to $74+81f < 87+96f$, we get that if there is $n+1 \in 87+96f$, then $87+96f$ and

$n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

In the same way, on the bunch of operational routes of $15+12c$, each reader can also conclude other 3 kinds of $15+12c$ derived from first satisfactory operational results to fit the conjecture, as listed below.

- 4). Pursuant to $c=2d+1$, $d=2e$, $e=2f$, $f=2g+1$ and $g=2h+1$ to get $c=32h+25$, then there is $15+12c=315+384h$ derived from $200+243h$ where the mark (4);
- 5). Pursuant to $c=2d$, $d=2e+1$, $e=2f$, $f=2g+1$ and $g=2h$ to get $c=32h+10$, then there is $15+12c=135+384h$ derived from $86+243h$ where the mark (5);
- 6). Pursuant to $c=2d$, $d=2e$, $e=2f$, $f=2g$ and $g=2h$ to get $c=32h$, then there is $15+12c=15+384h$ derived from $10+243h$ where the mark (6).

Secondly, we start with $19+12c$ to operate continuously by the operational rule, as listed below.

$$19+12c \rightarrow 58+36c \rightarrow 29+18c \rightarrow 88+54c \rightarrow 44+27c \clubsuit$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \begin{array}{cc}
 d=2e: 11+27e \text{ (}\alpha\text{)} & e=2f: 37+81f \text{ (}\beta\text{)} \\
 \clubsuit 44+27c \downarrow \rightarrow c=2d: 22+27d \uparrow \rightarrow d=2e+1: 148+162e \rightarrow 74+81e \uparrow \rightarrow e=2f+1: 466+486f \heartsuit \\
 c=2d+1: 214+162d \rightarrow 107+81d \downarrow \rightarrow d=2e: 322+486e \spadesuit & \\
 d=2e+1: 94+81e \downarrow \rightarrow e=2f: 47+81f \text{ (}\gamma\text{)} & \\
 e=2f+1: 526+486f \blacklozenge & \\
 \\
 g=2h: 119+243h \text{ (}\delta\text{)} & \dots \\
 f=2g+1: 238+243g \uparrow \rightarrow g=2h+1: 1444+1458h \rightarrow 722+729h \uparrow \rightarrow \dots & \\
 \heartsuit 466+486f \rightarrow 233+243f \uparrow \rightarrow f=2g: 700+1458g \rightarrow 350+729g \downarrow \rightarrow g=2h+1: 3238+4374h \downarrow & \\
 g=2h: 175+729h \downarrow \rightarrow \dots & \dots \\
 \dots & \\
 g=2h+1: 172+243h \text{ (}\epsilon\text{)} & \\
 f=2g: 101+243g \uparrow \rightarrow g=2h: 304+1458h \rightarrow \dots & \\
 e=2f+1: 202+243f \uparrow \rightarrow f=2g+1: 1336+1458g \rightarrow \dots & \\
 \spadesuit 322+486e \rightarrow 161+243e \uparrow \rightarrow e=2f: 484+1458f \rightarrow \dots & \\
 \\
 \blacklozenge 526+486f \rightarrow 263+243f \downarrow \rightarrow f=2g: 790+1458g \rightarrow \dots & \\
 f=2g+1: 253+243g \downarrow \rightarrow g=2h+1: 248+243h \text{ (}\zeta\text{)} & \\
 g=2h: 760+1458h \rightarrow \dots &
 \end{array}
 \end{array}$$

As listed above, on the bunch of operational routes of $19+12c$, we first conclude following 3 kinds of $19+12c$ derived from first satisfactory operational results to fit the conjecture.

1). From $c = 2d$ and $d = 2e$ to get $c = 2d = 4e$, then there are $19+12c = 19+48e = 19+3 \times 2^4e \rightarrow 58+3^2 \times 2^4e \rightarrow 29+3^2 \times 2^3e \rightarrow 88+3^3 \times 2^3e \rightarrow 44+3^3 \times 2^2e \rightarrow 22+3^3 \times 2e \rightarrow 11+27e$ where the mark (α).

Due to $11+27e < 19+48e$, we get that if there is $n+1 \in 19+48e$, then $19+48e$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

2). From $c=2d$, $d=2e+1$ and $e=2f$ to get $c=2d=2(2e+1)=4e+2=8f+2$, then there are $19+12c=43+96f=43+3 \times 2^5f \rightarrow 130+3^2 \times 2^5f \rightarrow 65+3^2 \times 2^4f \rightarrow 196+3^3 \times 2^4f \rightarrow 98+3^3 \times 2^3f \rightarrow 49+3^3 \times 2^2f \rightarrow 148+3^4 \times 2^2f \rightarrow 74+3^4 \times 2^1f \rightarrow 37+81f$ where the mark (β).

Due to $37+81f < 43+96f$, we get that if there is $n+1 \in 43+96f$, then $43+96f$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

3). From $c=2d+1$, $d=2e+1$ and $e=2f$ to get $c=2d+1=4e+3=8f+3$, then there are $19+12c=55+96f=55+3 \times 2^5f \rightarrow 166+3^2 \times 2^5f \rightarrow 83+3^2 \times 2^4f \rightarrow 250+3^3 \times 2^4f \rightarrow 125+3^3 \times 2^3f \rightarrow 376+3^4 \times 2^3f \rightarrow 188+3^4 \times 2^2f \rightarrow 94+3^4 \times 2^1f \rightarrow 47+81f$ where the mark (γ).

Due to $47+81f < 55+96f$, we get that if there is $n+1 \in 55+96f$, then $55+96f$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture, according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

In the same way, on the bunch of operational routes of $19+12c$, each reader can also conclude other 3 kinds of $19+12c$ derived from first satisfactory operational results to fit the conjecture, as listed below.

4). Pursuant to $c=2d$, $d=2e+1$, $e=2f+1$, $f=2g+1$ and $g=2h$ to get $c=32h+4$, then there is $19+12c=187+384h$ derived from $119+243h$ where the mark (δ);

5). Pursuant to $c=2d+1$, $d=2e$, $e=2f+1$, $f=2g$ and $g=2h+1$ to get $c=32h+21$, then there is $19+12c=271+384h$ derived from $172+243h$ where the mark (ϵ);

6). Pursuant to $c=2d+1$, $d=2e+1$, $e=2f+1$, $f=2g+1$ and $g=2h+1$ to get $c=32h+31$ then there is $19+12c=391+384h$ derived from $248+243h$ where the mark (ζ).

So far, take into account what we and each reader have done, there are altogether 6 kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ to fit the conjecture.

It follows that if $n+1$ belongs in any kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ derived from first satisfactory operational result, then, that kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ and $n+1$ fit the conjecture according to Theorem 1 and Lemma 3.

By now, we analyze two bunches of operational routes of $15+12c$ and $19+12c$ whether they are related, as described below.

Due to $c \geq 1$, there are infinitely more odd numbers of $15+12c/19+12c$, whether they belong to infinite or finite more kinds, boil down to all kinds can only be on the bunch of operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$.

For variables on operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$, they are often seen as having many, however, in fact, they can be converted into a common variable, otherwise, any kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ is in the hide always.

Since there is a common variable, not only allows you to compare the size between a certain operational result and a kind of $15+12c/19+12c$, but also let you know that every two operational routes on the bunch of operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$, they either directly intersect or indirectly connect, since they can be extended enough.

Besides, not only one kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ derives from first satisfactory operational result, but also there is the case where at least two kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ derive from a satisfactory operational result, such as $15+12(4+2^{55}\times 3^2y)$ and $15+12(8+2^{32}\times 3^{17}y)$ are derived from $61+2^3\times 3^{37}y$.

In some cases, an operational route of $15+12c$ and an operational route of $19+12c$ coincide partially or intersect from each other, such as start with $15+12(1+2^{57}y)$ to operate via five steps in a row, you get $19+12(1+2^{54}\times 3^2y)$.

As stated, we have analyzed these two bunches of operational routes of $15+12c$ and $19+12c$, and that we are possessed of the enough evidences to prove that all unproven kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ fit the conjecture.

Under these circumstances, let us prove all unproven kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ from each other's- opposite directions, in following paragraphs.

Firstly, we start with proven 6 kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ to expand the scope of proven kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ continuously.

According to Theorem 1 and Theorem 2, all integer expressions on at least one operational route via each of proven 6 kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ are proved to fit the conjecture.

After that, all integer expressions which fit the conjecture are turned into proven integer expressions.

Next, according to Lemma 1 and Lemma 2, all integer expressions on successive intersecting operational routes via each of proven integer expressions are proved to fit the conjecture.

After that, all integer expressions which fit the conjecture are turned into proven integer expressions.

The rest can be deduced in batches by analogy. According to Lemma 1 and Lemma 2, proven integer expressions on the bunch's operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$ are getting more and more.

In theory, by doing in this way and according to Lemma 1 and Lemma 2, the scope of proven integer expressions is successively extended, so after doing it an infinite number of times, all integer expressions on the bunch's operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$ are proved to fit the conjecture.

Because the bunch of operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$ consists of operational routes whose each starts with an integer expression of $15+12c/19+12c$.

Now that all integer expressions on the bunch of operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$ have seen proved to fit the conjecture, undoubtedly, all integer expressions of $15+12c/19+12c$ have seen proved too to fit the conjecture, since all integer expressions on the bunch's operational routes of $15+12c/19+12c$ contain all integer expressions of $15+12c/19+12c$.

Secondly, we start with each unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ to operate by the operational rule, until first satisfactory operational result of the unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ appears on an operational route via the unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ or on an operational route related to it.

First of all, how do you present an unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$?

Since there is only the variable c in $15+12c/19+12c$, if the c value in some kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ is not equal to any of c values in all proven kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$, then this kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ is exactly an unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$.

In addition, before continuing to prove unproved kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$, there have been 6 proven kind of $15+12c/19+12c$. As proved above, they respectively are: when $c=4e+3, 8f+5, 8f+6, 32h+25, 32h+10$ and $32h$, such that $15+12c$ have been proved to fit the conjecture; when $c=4e, 8f+2, 8f+3, 32h+4, 32h+21$ and $32h+31$, such that $19+12c$ have been proved to fit the conjecture, so you don't have to worry about having no proven kind of $15+12c/19+12c$.

Now that we can find unproved kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ in turn, also are possessed of the operational rule and criteria for judging operational results, then we can prove each unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ to fit the conjecture, so apply and can only apply one of the following three ways.

(1) On an operational route via an unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$, if there is an integer expression that is less than the unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$, then the unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ is proved to fit the conjecture, according to Theorem 1.

(2) If an operational route via an unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ and an operational route via a proven kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ intersect, then the unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ is proved to fit the conjecture, according

to Lemma 2.

(3) If an operational route via an unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ and an operational route via a proven kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ are in indirect connection, then the unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ is proved to fit the conjecture, according to Lemma 2.

As one kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ after another is proved, then proven kinds of $15+12c/19+12c$ are getting more and more, like so, it goes on infinitely, up to all unproved kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ are proved to fit the conjecture.

According to the bidirectional proofs which have been given above, such that all kind of $15+12c/19+12c$ have been proved to fit the conjecture.

Therefore, if $n+1$ belongs in a kind of $15+12c/19+12c$, then $n+1$ is proved to fit the conjecture, accord to Lemma 3.

7. Make a Summary and Reach the Conclusion

To sum up, $n+1$ has been proved to fit the conjecture, whether $n+1$ belongs in which sort of odd numbers or which kind of odd numbers, or it is exactly an even number.

We can also prove integers $n+2$, $n+3$ etc. up to every integer that is greater than $n+1$ to fit the conjecture, in the light of the old way of doing thing.

The proof was thus brought to a close. As a consequence, the Collatz conjecture is tenable.

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